

LEARNING PROCESSES THROUGH READING

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10116613

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Pedagogue. PhD student in Educational Sciences at the Facultad Interamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Asunción, Paraguay. srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

Renata Mônica Pacheco Nichio

Pedagogue. Teacher at the Municipal Education Network of Cariacica - ES. Master's student in Educational Sciences at the Facultad Interamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Asunción, Paraguay. renatamonica768@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This article deals with the subject related to learning processes through reading. It is a subject that remains current, because the decoding of the symbols of nature, that is, their previous reading, so that they could be known and interpreted until they are understood is an action inherent to human thought. Here, specifically, it is about the reading of books, texts, in which it is intended that the child, of school age, does so in an acinct way. This is a bibliographical study, based on the thoughts of authors who deal with the subject and on the pedagogical practice, translated through the realization of experiences with the practice of teaching reading in the classroom. Reading, by favoring the dialectic relationship between the reader and the elements elaborated by the author (ideas and images), allows the establishment of the construction of meanings from the connection with the reader's daily life and the previously acquired knowledge, resulting in the improvement of the capacity to learn, overcoming the mere reception of contents, for which there is not always the due cognitive interest. For the production and development of reading, motivation is needed not only from external factors (contact with the book, economic conditions to acquire it), but mainly from internal factors (having a pleasant and meaningful experience, wanting to read, reading for some purpose).

Keywords: Reading. Reading teaching. Reading and interpretation. Reading experiences.

INTRODUCTION

The growing number of functionally illiterate people, people who, despite attending school for 8 (eight) years or more, are not capable of reading and interpreting with autonomy and intellectual security, have demonstrated the ineffectiveness of the teaching and learning techniques applied in schools. elementary school and this cognitive deficiency becomes

chronic, persisting throughout life, because the situation of lack of command of the vernacular language and its canons has become an endemic problem and, as a result, speaking incorrectly, reading in any way, writing texts without nexus, cohesion, coherence and logical cadence began to be interpreted as something extremely normal, with those who preserve grammar as an expression of literary aberrations and linguistic virtuosity.

The principle that guides the correct use of the vernacular language is respect for it; which makes everyone who comes into contact with her understand how much she represents for the nation. Therefore, it has become a great challenge for institutional education to rethink a curricular proposal that emphasizes the construction of knowledge and the acquisition of significant learning regarding the use and expression of the Portuguese language.

As long as the teacher is the only one to select content and texts without providing opportunities for discussion and opinion outside the textbook, disrespecting the pace and progress, although slow, of the student who cannot see any meaning in the content offered, expecting that learning can be achieved in the When it comes to reading, it becomes a whim.

Cavalcanti (1997) argues that, during expression and writing classes,

The teacher must be careful to allow his students to exercise themselves in discovering reading and to be able to propose their favorite works to their colleagues, even if their choice goes against the taste of the teacher himself, who must not be intimidated by his students' choice or by the rejection of a certain work (CAVALCANTI, 1997, p. 15).

Learning cannot be reduced to a mechanical aspect or a list of skills or grammatical content; and should be conceived as a process of extracting and composing fundamental meanings from what the student already knows in literary terms or from what he likes to read, which is an object of interest to him, for a reframing or modification of previous concepts, which is not occurs spontaneously; therefore, he ends up suffering intervention from the teacher most of the time he is at school. In this way, the importance of interpersonal relationships is confirmed as a way of contacting other peers and, with or through these others, acquiring new knowledge and even resizing existing ones.

Ferrero (2004) argues that,

In the development of reading (...), considered as a cognitive process, there is an effective construction of organizing principles that not only cannot be derived solely from external experience, but are also contrary to it; they are contrary, including to systematic school teaching and non-systematic information (FERRERO, 2004, p. 20).

Reading, by favoring the dialectical relationship between the reader and the elements elaborated by the author (ideas and images), allows the establishment of the construction of meanings based on the link with the reader's daily life and previously acquired knowledge, resulting in the improvement of capacity of learning, going beyond the mere reception of content, for which there is not always due cognitive interest.

In the past, reading was simply considered as a means of receiving a message, based on memorization and competition. Students memorized immense classic texts and participated in debates, without there being reflection or discussion about what was repeated.

Currently, with increasing access to books, reading is defined as a process through which there are countless possibilities for interpreting and understanding written language. At the same time, the skills of decoding and contributing objectives, ideas and experiences to the text are skillfully handled, generating involvement in a process of continuous prediction and inference, which is based on the information provided by the text and on one's own background, in a process that allows evidence or rejects the predictions and inferences already mentioned.

Reading is no longer about memorization, repetition, but rather an interaction between the individual and the text, with an analytical and interpretative confrontation of the experiences that the reader has. This intellectual process contributes to the development of abstract thinking, because the better the quality and quantity of reading, the greater the ability to learn as a whole, enabling the student to have a vast knowledge of the history of their present moment, social and cultural values of the society to which he belongs. Through stories, legends, journalistic texts and poetry, the individual can carry out a comprehensive reading autonomously, also using the text to learn as an instrument that allows them to analyze, compare and answer the questions that cross them as empirical and logical challenges.

For the production and development of reading, motivation is necessary not only from external factors (contact with the book, economic conditions to acquire it), but mainly from internal factors (having a pleasurable and meaningful experience, wanting to read, reading for some purpose).). And, nowadays, consumed by immediacy, a chaotic situation is emerging in which the majority of students are suffering from intermittent intellectual impoverishment and consequently linguistic impoverishment, caused by the difficulties in learning and the increasingly depleted contact with reading, the norm cultured and with knowledge of the vernacular language and its canons. It is in this space that the pedagogical action of the committed teacher takes place; who acts as someone who promotes meaningful learning situations, capable of revitalizing the desire to read, removing educational obstacles already

crystallized by the lack of knowledge of some teachers regarding the learning process and the mechanisms that lead to reading comprehension.

WHERE, WHEN AND HOW YOU START LEARNING TO READ

In everyday life, the individual lives surrounded by texts that serve to convince, inform, communicate, express all types of ideas and feelings. Everyone, without exception, lives with a series of texts printed on different objects and places, and participates in countless situations in which reading is present and/or necessary. Contact with the world of images and signs makes it possible to understand not only the situations of use and functions of texts, but also their linguistic characteristics.

What is observed in schools in relation to reading, in general, is a great uniformity of practices, revolving around a single conception in which reading is just *the oral translation of the written one*. This generates a mechanical, meaningless reading, in which the school places a lot of importance, based on the teacher's manuals, trying to follow them to the letter, as is done with medical and culinary recipes. This behavior comes from the lack of projects that have reading as one of the guiding principles of an interdisciplinary pedagogical practice.

In order to change this archaic practice devoid of pedagogical criteria, it is a prerequisite to create mechanisms that awaken the reader, to make an effort to understand the child's psychic development, who begins to learn from intrauterine life, when he perceives and reacts to the sensations passed on by the mother. And, in the first months of life, she communicates through a smile, then a syllable that names everything, until she can articulate words and sentences. And it continues throughout life, in constant interaction with the social environment, wherever it is located. These skills must be well developed in the preschool phase, so that the child, with his entire body schema worked out, associated with cognitive potential, enters the world of books and interactive reading with ease.

According to Ferreiro (2001),

Children try to systematize what they learn in language learning and in all domains of knowledge, they test the organization achieved through affective acts of using acquired knowledge, and restructure when they discover that the previous organization is incomparable with the data of the experience (FERREIRO, 2001, p. 31).

In this way, the close connection between reading ages and the stage of development in which the child is at is evident. These phases are not rigid; For this reason, they happen at

different times in each person's life, and there is no way to determine them precisely; Everything we have as empirical knowledge serves as a guiding instrument for pedagogical work in teaching and learning to read. According to Ferreiro (2001, p. 61), individuals “must demonstrate that they have the skills defined as prerequisites to be able to enter a certain level of school”.

Therefore, it is essential to note that every person, to become a reader, goes through phases and returns to them when they need to mature, considering that the individual reader originates from the social and cultural environment, together with other factors such as environmental conditions, appeals of the media, differentiated family education, religion, reader-non-reader models that the child lives with and which can interfere with their preferences and literary dynamics.

Therefore, the school must resort to phases without rigidity, to enable the discussion of selection criteria and reading suggestions to be offered to students, according to their interests, so that desire is instigated through systematic contact with good materials, diversity of texts and with adult readers who have effective practices, thus preventing them from developing reading difficulties. “It is necessary to share with the class the characteristics of the characters, comment and get everyone to talk about the story, ask the children to remember the plot, ask questions and let them express their doubts” (REVISTA ESCOLA, 2005, p. 26) .

Reading is like an unnatural behavior; and, for this reason, it must be built, little by little, producing knowledge about the state of development of individual and collective lecto-writing. Therefore, this knowledge of the process of evolution of learning to read is fundamental for the teacher and the psychopedagogue to help the child to advance through the highlighted standards, as there may be variations between the level of learning and the chronological age that the individual presents, as they are opportunities for social coexistence and familiarity with the literate world and good pedagogical guidance that will determine the quality of each reader and their development potential.

READING AND COMPREHENSION

Among the reading difficulties faced by students, there is a lack of understanding the lexical meaning, as one of the biggest problems that lead to failure in learning to read. It was observed that students respond based on their unfounded ideas, regardless of what is stated in the text. This demonstrates that students, when reading a text, start from their knowledge derived from common sense, to express their understanding of the topics covered, which leads

to a new reading of reality, they were not properly guided, as they only repeat what they supposedly know and have it as truth; acting as signal decipherers.

The difficulty in understanding is more harmful than the lack of knowledge of the sign, as it does not allow the reader to interact with the universe presented by the author, through his text; As a result, the student is prevented from reconstituting any type of reading. Understanding a text is giving it meaning, activating complex mental processes, in which this involvement leads to constructing meanings based on the information acquired during the act of reading and associating your particular discoveries with your prior knowledge, comparing it with common sense knowledge. .

Thus, for the student to reach understanding, they must be able to relate reading with observation of reality, establishing meanings, agreements and dissonances between them. To this end, there is a need for teacher guidance in the systematization of collective situations with exchanges of ideas and information about the readings, with questions constructed by the desire for information and not evaluation, as commonly occurs in the classroom. And also, the creation of individualized situations, through slow and gradual work that involves various levels of understanding, using increasingly complex tasks; however, possible to meet the cognitive and intellectual levels of students, providing didactic and pedagogical support, so that the child can redefine their capacity for intellectual interpretation.

READING COMPREHENSION STRATEGY

Society lives in constant change: in values, meanings, attitudes, conceptions and political systems; just like the most diverse institutions, from the family, its beliefs to the school and its teaching methods. Teaching professionals still today emphasize the decoding of words as an end in itself, disregarding the construction of meanings, which makes it impossible to develop comprehensive reading, although one change is evident: the effort and importance that teachers give to their students. elements that intervene in the learning process, in the tireless search to supply knowledge and conditions to better prepare the student to acquire reading. However, this search has not proved to be sufficient to modify educational praxis. It ends that,

Scholars, who today do nothing more than *thumb* [turn the pages with their finger], end up completely losing the ability to think for themselves. As they read, they don't think. Scholars spend all their energy saying yes or no on criticizing what others think – they themselves no longer have the capacity to think (ALVES, 1999, p. 58).

Reading is a constant process of creating and verifying predictions through which written language is understood. Consequently, to read it will be essential to use various paths and strategies until understanding is achieved. The strategies applied, in teaching and intervention practices, can be cognitive, automatic and unconscious as they have not yet reached the level of consciousness, enabling quick and efficient reading, through the activation of prior knowledge, the inferential process of the principles of coherence thematic, parsimony, relevance and canonicity, among others. These elements are extremely important for the acquisition of comprehensive reading.

METACOGNITIVE STRATEGY

Metacognitive strategies govern the reader's conscious behavior, in which objectives contribute to the formulation of hypotheses (both about structure and content), making global and instantaneous knowledge of words and phrases possible. These strategies help the reader understand the text, extracting from it what interests them according to their objectives, done through individual reading to allow progress and rewind that leads to stopping, thinking, recapitulating and relating the information with the knowledge already acquired, deciding what is relevant or secondary. It is an internal process; but, that it must be taught; It's not instinctive. However, the school does not provide students with the opportunity to develop reading strategies and this generally happens as a pretext to improve diction, copying or carrying out activities in the textbook. Reading, like any other intelligent act, requires the individual to make anticipations, construct hypotheses about the meaning, and for this it is necessary to plan reading classes so that the teacher consciously provokes such anticipations and didactic situations.

Therefore, to understand, teachers need to teach how to use facilitating strategies that should be part of the student's background so that they can be used autonomously in the future by determining objectives, working in shared or individual reading situations, as an active reader, in which it establishes a dialogue with different textual typologies, which differs from the reality experienced in schools.

ANALYSIS OF THE REAL IN SEARCH OF THE IDEAL

Understanding and interpreting text are made difficult and even blocked by several factors, one of the main ones being deficiencies in the literacy process, that is, at the beginning

of the schooling process, when the child has their first formal contacts with reading and reading-writing (its symbols and codes). It is in the initial phase that there is the opportunity to encourage students' reading habits and tastes, and all of this is linked, in a very intimate way, to the learning methodology used in the initial grades. When the child arrives at school he already knows how to speak and think, because "he has learned to speak and understand what is said to him, revealing a process of language acquisition that has had great development from approximately the first year of age" (CAGLIARI, 1990, p. 16). However, understanding the lexical system is highly complex and this requires specific pedagogical actions, designed with a specific purpose, which is to live, co-exist and survive in a literate world, full of symbols that require deciphering by the individual, because if this is not the case, your understanding of it will always be deficient, mediocre.

No one denies children access to linguistic information before they are speakers; no one proposes a plan for presenting this linguistic information in a predetermined sequence. But, at school, despite pedagogical proposals, reading has defined objectives, such as building general knowledge. From this perspective, literacy contradicts all the conditions for learning to read, as it ignores the information brought by the student in everyday life such as sound and visual stimuli from signs, labels, music, functioning as an obstacle to the transformation and elaboration of knowledge when the child demands rigorous coherence in its construction process. This intellectual construction is not a product "merely of the mass of individuals that compose them, of the territories they occupy, of the things they use and the movements they execute. They are made, above all, with the ideas that individuals have of themselves" (ALVES, 1999, p. 25).

When teachers understand the dimension of reading praxis and apply their processes in order to promote the development of the reading personality in students, the school will be fulfilling its true role of inserting the child into a literate society, which should begin from pre-school, providing them with the opportunity to read or *listen* to diverse texts to stimulate interest in the content of the book, as well as educational games, drawings and illustrations of stories, participation in the audience of lectures by the authors of the books, which greatly awakens the curiosity of beginners in reading.

Teachers must not only take into account students' achievement levels, but also help develop the skills of understanding and reading the different forms of language in society.

According to the PCNs (Portuguese Language, 1997),

Adequate educational practice (...) considers the interests and motivations of students and guarantees learning for the formation of autonomous, critical, and participatory citizens, capable of acting with competence, dignity and responsibility in the society in which we live (BRAZIL, PCN, 1997, p. 33).

archaic practices, which are not at all pedagogical, in which the conception of learning confuses understanding with the repetition of the right answer, requiring more the memorization of data than the unfolding of the student's potential in cognitive construction, interaction and interlocution, it will be difficult to achieve autonomy to act on textual understanding. This practice leads students to complete “elementary education without knowing how to read and write. This is after studying eight years of school (...) or, without also understanding and knowing how to use what you read. In both cases, illiteracy levels are high” (SOARES, 2003, p. 3).

To change this reality, knowledge on how to stimulate the student, a knowledgeable, talented and curious individual, who, in order to learn, needs to be worked on integrally, through psychomotricity and a conception that seeks interaction between the comprehensive reading with a concrete meaning, in which the assistance of the psychopedagogue is very important, a professional who has a wealth of epistemological and experience to build a pedagogical project together with the school's pedagogical team, in which reading is understood as a learning instrument meaningful and pragmatic.

Ferrero argues that,

Literacy development undoubtedly occurs in a social environment. But social practices, like social information, are not received passively by children. When they try to understand, they necessarily transform the content received. Furthermore, in order to record the information, they transform it. This is a profound meaning of the notion of assimilation (FERRERO, 2004, p. 22).

Therefore, it is urgent to change it in public schools, even if this means facing an already consolidated and traditional discourse, with its tendency to preserve archaic and bankrupt pedagogical practices immutable, under the pretext of maintaining the already established order, thus escaping the function explicit approach to developing children's intellect through pedagogical experience.

The school must face the great challenge and, respecting individuality, train readers and not just individuals, holders of diplomas, who can *decipher* the written system: thus, train individuals endowed with critical thinking, capable of reading between the lines and assuming their own position facing the reading with which they interact, it is up to educators to teach all

students literacy, aiming to ensure them opportunities to read as a relevant instrument for their cognitive development.

TEACHING READING

The pedagogical practices applied to learning to read have not had the desired effect of training student readers, capable of understanding the text, this is when they do not induce complete disinterest or even inhibit the ability to continue learning.

It is necessary to consider that it is not enough for the teacher to know what needs to be done; he must wish to carry out his practice with another structure. Thus, action plans, reading projects and creative activities must leave the paper and become reality in the classroom, no matter how much this breaks the routine, changes the methodology or requires new movements from the educator. There is a very traditional way of teaching, which is not easy to change. However, there is a model of more traditional teachers, although due to the comfort and convenience with which they work or *apply* their classes, it is even more difficult to renew themselves.

ENCOURAGE READING: TEACHER'S TASK

It is necessary to transform the school into a space where reading is a living and constant practice, perceived as a valuable instrument that allows one to elaborate and organize one's own thoughts, through the practice of interpreting and producing texts. Rubem Alves (1999, p. 61) advises: "If such texts please you, great. Otherwise, don't continue, because mandatory reading is as absurd as talking about mandatory happiness."

Reading is a social practice and it is up to the school, first of all, to make students take ownership of it. Therefore, students who have the desire to learn reach the best level of reading comprehension. It must be recognized that awakening the desire to read in students is a daily task at school; It is also known that not everything is always successful. In Brazil, the precarious training of teachers and those responsible for guiding them, as well as training them, is yet another negative element that undermines educational objectives. When it comes to training critical readers, the combination of a school resistant to change and poorly prepared teaching staff constitutes a solid obstacle. For the transformation of practices centered on conceptions of reading, theoretically outdated, to occur, one must understand the nature of the act of reading, which requires going through reflection on what writing represents in pedagogical and

sociological terms, which demands time, study and knowledge not always available to a large part of the teaching staff, especially those who work in the public education network.

Therefore, it is up to the public authorities to implement continuous training, during working hours, in order to enable a constructive reflection on practice, supported by theoretical deepening aimed at providing opportunities for the construction of professional skills and specific knowledge necessary for every teacher, in their role as , in addition to being the one who teaches, also guides, facilitates, assists, and provides the necessary support for the student to learn in affirmation with the new times, aspirations and destinies so differentiated by schools in the formation of competent, creative, autonomous students, capable of solve problems of all kinds.

THE TRAINING OF THE READER

As reading is a significant and valuable experience for children's learning, it must be presented in a motivating way, always encouraging them to want to delve deeper, creating a positive atmosphere in the classroom, to lead them towards reading, through affection, looking for the best in students and drawing their attention to the positive aspects of this ability, helping them to satisfy current needs and future occupations throughout their lives. For all this and much more, the teacher's influence in the classroom is essential for the development of readers.

Reading can be a source of joy. To this end, the teacher must be patient, encouraging, support the students' learning efforts, creating an environment where there is a variety of subject genres, providing positive role models and facilitating learning through texts, communicating verbally and non-verbally their feelings about reading. "Through a reconsideration of the reading process and the reader's activity, which brought factors such as significant anticipation and linguistic knowledge that the reader brings to the task to the foreground" (FERREIRO, 2004, p. 83).

The critical reader is the cooperative reader, who reconstructs the world from a text; does not act as a mere signal decipherer; mobilizes their knowledge to give coherence to their possibilities in the text; is productive, becomes an enunciator, subject of the reading process and not an object and, as such, reconstructs the text with his words, synthesizing and interpreting, perceiving the meanings hidden in the words.

To have students with positive attitudes towards reading, who will continue to read, even long after they have finished elementary education, time must be allocated for silent reading, reading aloud and for intellectual discussion about what has been proposed. reading.

THE FAMILY AND LEARNING TO READ

Bearing in mind that, in the past, when a child entered the extra-family world, it was expected that he would represent his family well, being a good student, learning his lessons and transferring the relationship of obedience learned at home to his teachers. This shows the responsibility mainly of the mother, to teach how to perceive the world and how to position herself in it to function well in society. However, today this pedagogical participation of the mother becomes precarious, due to the need for the mother to help her husband or replace him in maintaining the house. This separation leads some students, regardless of their social class, to experience difficulties in learning due to a lack of guidance and encouragement.

Parents' contribution to encouraging reading should begin from the child's first year of life, reading to them, talking about the text, showing them the pictures and naming the things they see. In this way, they will be developing language and interest in books, as it can be determined that the role of parents in their children's development in reading is great, because by practicing reading in the family environment from an early age, children will have a greater chance of being successful in learning, especially if parents communicate to their children the importance of having a good academic performance, believing in their success, maintaining direct contact with the school and, finally, encouraging interaction with instructional materials, such as newspapers, books, magazines, letters, toys and lots of love when transmitting knowledge.

The family strongly influences the formation of the reader. Parents who read set a good example; therefore, it is natural for children to act by imitation, also acquiring the habit of reading. When parents read to their children, they are not only encouraging, but also actively participating in the construction of the individual reader, helping them learn to extract meanings from the text and interact successfully at school and in life.

Some parents are unaware of the importance of their task of demonstrating interest in work and studies and get lost in the excessive contemporary offer of incentives for consumption. The contributions they can offer are varied, ranging from organizing time and place for study to gaining the capacity for autonomy to develop their own knowledge. This is offered in a home where there is emotional stability, where children feel welcomed.

When the family does not arouse interest in the children and they, despite methodological actions, are unable to progress in their studies, it is prudent to resort to psycho-pedagogical guidance in order to analyze the student's real difficulties so that they can advance cognitively.

CONCLUSION

Learning letters is directly linked to the social environment, as the consolidation of knowledge depends on the meanings they carry in relation to the students' social experience in the family, in the community, at work. The teaching-learning-social environment link implies the degree of reading comprehension in relation to the students' real possibilities in the face of the empirical and epistemological demands of the school.

During the period that the student attends primary school, it is expected that over these years they will progressively acquire a competence in relation to language that will enable them to solve problems in everyday life and even decode the linguistic symbols that surround and permeate their existence.

For this expectation to be realized, teaching reading must be organized in such a way that students are capable of expanding the use of language in private settings, knowing how to speak and produce both oral and written texts, using different recording models, including the most formal of the linguistic variety, respecting and knowing the different spoken linguistic varieties and thus being able to understand the oral and written texts that they encounter in their day-to-day situations, autonomously.

In this way, it is expressed that mastery of the language is closely related to the possibility of full social participation, as it is through it that man communicates, has access to information, expresses and defends points of view, shares or constructs world views. , produces and reproduces experiences, building knowledge.

It is concluded that, in general, any human activity carried out in the environment in which they live can lead to learning, as long as the individual is able to read the symbols involved. Since human beings are born, they are learning and continue to learn throughout their lives. Individuals are always learning, at home, on the street, at work, at school, in existential experiences. In order for you to understand and transform this entire experience into learning, you need to learn to read and interpret them.

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